

THE MOST IMPORTANT PRESCRIPTION ABBREVIATION

Nasimova Sokhiba Yakhyaevna

Assistant teacher of the Department of Languages, Samarkand State Medical University

Stephy Sabu

The 1 st year Student of International Faculty, Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract: This abstract tells us about the important prescription abbreviation, their beginning, where they originated from, most commonly used abbreviations and their importance in day to day and medical life.

Key words: prescription, Pharmacopoeia, abbreviation, patronymic, initial, health

INTRODUCTION

Each prescription has the following details (which are checked at the pharmacy when accepting the prescription from the patient:

The name of the health care facility, its address and telephone number - usually in the form of a rectangular stamp in the upper left corner. Name of the type of prescription form (148, 107, special form, etc.)

Series and recipe number (except 107/y)

Prescription date

Full name of the patient (first and patronymic in the form of initials), his age (in the form of date of birth), address, medical history number (not for form 107/y)

Full name of the doctor (name and patronymic in the form of initials) who wrote the prescription

The actual prescription (finished medicine or instructions to the pharmacy to produce it extemporaneously)

Doctor's signature

Stamp of health care facility "For prescriptions" (not for form 107/u)

Doctor's personal stamp

Expiration date of the prescription (indicated by the doctor)

Only for special forms - stamp of the medical facility and signature of the chief physician (chief of medicine)

In special cases (for example, for chronically ill people or when intentionally overprescribing potent substances), the top of the prescription form may be marked “Chronically ill” or “For special purposes.” Then, pharmacists (pharmacists) pay special attention to this and handle the prescription according to the situation. Such notes are certified by the doctor’s signature and the seal of the health care facility.

Prescriptions for potent drugs located on the PCU, as well as for forms containing ethyl alcohol, remain in the pharmacy. In return, the patient is given a signature - a special form with an oblique yellow stripe on the front side. The signature does not have legal force (that is, it cannot be used to obtain medicine at the pharmacy), however, when the patient visits the doctor again, he will thus be able to remember what medicine was prescribed to him last time and the doctor, if necessary, will be able to write a new prescription using the old signature. However, in practice the signature is often not issued.

The prescription forms themselves can be written out for a finished dosage form, or with instructions to the pharmacy to prepare the dosage form extemporaneously. Currently in Russia the following are extemporaneously prepared: powders, ointments, solutions for oral administration (potions), solutions for external use, nasal drops, eye drops (rarely), infusions (rarely), decoctions (rarely).

In the case of an extemporaneous prescription, the doctor must take into account the personal characteristics of the patient, the compatibility of the ingredients and be guided by the requirements of the current State Pharmacopoeia, orders of the Ministry of Health and other regulations that have legal force.

The prescription abbreviation were made to simplify the work of physician who rather have to write the entire word but for instead agreed upon using certain smaller version of the word which would be under stood by both the physician and the patient.

Some of the common abbreviations are:

Tbsp – Tablespoon

Tsp – Teaspoon

w/o – Without

x – Times

In our country like India prescriptions are generally written in English but some words, some Latin words and some abbreviations are used in different parts of the world to make it easier for the pharmacist who reads the prescription.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-2, Issue-1

The symbol commonly used for prescription is Rx which is the abbreviated form of the word 'recipere' which means to take.

In this case, a prescription was issued for a complex combination ointment.

Rp.: - short for the Latin word "recipe" - take. Next is a list of components that need to be taken to prepare the ointment (components are written in Latin in the genitive case). The first component is written after the colon, all other components are strictly (!) below it.

Menthol and Novocaine - (ana, abbreviation aa with a line above the letters) "equally" 0.1 g, that is, 100 mg of each.

Adrenaline hydrochloride solution 0.1% - drops (guttas) 10 (according to tradition, the number of drops is written in Roman numerals)

Zinc oxide 1 g

Lanolin 5 g - a component of the ointment base is usually written at the end of the recipe

Vaseline 15 g - the second component of the ointment base

Misce ut fiat unguentum - Mix to make an ointment

Yes. Signa - Give it out. Label. Nose ointment.

There according to some sources its known that the medical abbreviation are generally in latin to maintain the secrecy of their remedies while writing medication as the common people wouldn't know then what they are being prescribed.

Now not only do we use abbreviation from Latin in medical field but many times we use them in day to day life writing without even knowing that their origin is from Latin.

i.e., is from id est which we generally use for that is,

e.g. Exempli gratia which we generally use for examples

etc., is from etcetra which in English is and so forth

vs., for versus which is against or for opposition

CONCLUSION

Prescription plays a very important role in medical field. Prescriptions have been followed from centuries, and the common abbreviations which are generally used are given above. Some are used so frequently but we didn't realize that they were abbreviations rather than actual words.

LITERATURE:

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-2, Issue-1

1. Yorova, S. K., & Khakberdiyeva, V. J. K. (2021). DOCTOR AND PATIENT. *Scientific progress*, 2(1), 1478-1480.
2. Yorova, S. (2023). TO STUDY MEDICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND GREEK LANGUAGES. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 166-170.
3. Aitmuratova, P., Yorova, S., & Esanova, M. (2023). THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN OUR LIFE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 161-164.
4. Yorova, S., Aytmuratova, P., Esanova, M., & Normurodova, S. (2023). PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE MEDICAL FIELD OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES. *Development and innovations in science*, 2(2), 10-13.
5. Yorova, S. K., & Iqbal, I. (2023). HISTORY OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(9), 158-164.
6. Normurodova, S. M., & Yorova, S. K. (2023). Nemis tili frazeologik birikmalari va tilning lug'at boyligi. *Science and Education*, 4(2), 1672-1675.
7. Yorova, S. K. (2017). The concept "health" in the English lingual culture. In *Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe: Achievements and Perspectives* (pp. 58-60).
8. Askarovich, B. S., Karimovna, Y. S., Sobirovich, X. Y., & Bakhodirovna, E. M. (2022). TEACHING MATH IN ENGLISH TO UNIVERSITIES AND INSTITUTIONS'STUDENTS FOR TAKING GMAT CERTIFICATE. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 1600-1604.
9. Yorova, S., & Nasirkhan, A. (2023). MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF TRAUMATOLOGICAL, ORTHOPEDICS AND NEUROSURGICAL DISEASES. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(11), 149-152.
10. Ёрова, С. К. (2023). ТИББИЙ НУТҚНИНГ КОГНИТИВ, МАДАНИЙ ВА ПРАГМАТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 3(2), 219-223.
11. Yorova, S. A. Y. O. R. A., & Nasimova, S. O. H. I. B. A. (2019). The ways of teaching languages at medical institutions.
12. Yaxyaevna, N. S. (2023). ANALYZING DIALECTS AND WRITTEN DOCUMENTS IN MIDDLE ENGLISH PERIOD. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 458-463.

13. Nasimova, S. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS THE SECOND LANGUAGE. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(11), 203-207.
14. Саматова, Г. Н., & Насимова, С. (2016). Прагматический подход к преподаванию на английском языке. *Научный альманах*, (6-1), 605-607.
15. Yaxyayevna, N. S. (2023). FONOLOGIYA VA UNING TURLARI. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(12), 5-9.
16. Nasimova Sohiba Yaxyayevna, & Mohammad Aftab Alam. (2023). INTRODUCTION INTO ANATOMICAL HISTOLOGICAL TERMINOLOGY. NOUN, GRAMMAR CATEGORIES OF NOUNS. DETERMINATIONS OF GENDER, STEM, VOCABULARY FORMS. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy Va Ijtimoiy-Gumanitar Fanlar Respublika Ilmiy Amaliy Konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 107–111. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/gumanitar/article/view/2974>
17. Nasimova Sohiba Yaxyayevna, & Taha Khalid. (2023). TOPIC PRESCRIPTION STRUCTURE OF PRESCRIPTION. *International Conference on Multidisciplinary Science*, 1(5), 210–214. Retrieved from <https://mjestjournal.com/index.php/icms/article/view/396>
18. Yakhyaevna, N. S. (2023). HISTORY OF ENGLISH WRITING DOCUMENTS IN THE MIDDLE AGES. *Research Focus*, 2(10), 41-45.
19. Yaxyayevna, N. S., & Alam, M. A. (2023). INTRODUCTION INTO ANATOMICAL HISTOLOGICAL TERMINOLOGY. NOUN, GRAMMAR CATEGORIES OF NOUNS. DETERMINATIONS OF GENDER, STEM, VOCABULARY FORMS. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 107-111.
20. Yaxyayevna, N. S., & Khalid, T. (2023, November). TOPIC PRESCRIPTION STRUCTURE OF PRESCRIPTION. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 210-214).
21. Yorova, S., & Nasimova, S. ELECTRONIC COLLECTED MATERIALS OF XI JUNIOR RESEARCHERS' CONFERENCE 2019 Linguistics, literature, philology 7 UDC 372.881 THE WAYS OF TEACHING LANGUAGES AT MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS Samarkand State Medical Institute.

22. Ilhomjonovna, S. K., & Parvina, O. (2020). Structural-Morphological Characteristics of Binary Tautologisms. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 2(12), 23-28.

23. Shamsiyev, K., Olimzoda, P., Saidova, K., & Ibragimova, D. (2023, February). APPROACHES TO TEACHING ACADEMIC WRITING. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 31-34).

24. Saidova, K., Ibragimova, D., Olimzoda, P., & Shamsiyev, K. (2023). INFLUENCE OF USING GAMES ON ENGLISH LESSONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 54-58.

25. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). Methodology For Using Computer Training Programs In English Lessons. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(13), 3358-3367.

26. Olimzoda, P. (2022). Usage of video as audiovisual materials in foreign language classes. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 800-803.

27. Нормуродова, Н., Уралова, Ч., & Олимзода, П. (2021). The role of extracurricular activities in foreign language teaching. *Общество и инновации*, 2(5/S), 12-16.

28. Parvina, O. (2023). TYPES OF TEXTBOOKS AND THEIR EVALUATION. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(4), 50-54.

29. Parvina, O. (2023). Theoretical and Methodological Foundations for the Formation of Communicative Competence of Medical Students. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education*, 1(3), 1-3.

30. Ibragimova, D. S., Saidova, K. I., & Olimzoda, P. THE EFFICACY OF PROFICIENT READING STRATEGIES IN ENHANCING READING COMPETENCIES.

31. Парвина, О. (2023). ОСНОВНАЯ РОЛЬ ДОПОЛНИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫК. *Research Focus*, 2(10), 69-74.

32. Fomina Mayde Anatolevna ,Shodikulova Aziza Zikirayayevna. (2023). DEONTOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF WINGED SAYINGS IN MEDICINE. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(10), 124-125. Retrieved from <http://www.eijmr.org/index.php/eijmr/article/view/343>

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-2, Issue-1

33. Фомина, М. А., & Шамсиев, К. К. (2020). КРЫЛАТЫЕ ИЗРЕЧЕНИЯ. *Глобус*, (1 (47)), 100-101.
34. Фомина, М. А., Бабаева, Д. Х., & Бекназарова, М. К. (2019). О СЛОВООБРАЗОВАНИИ В МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ. *Кронос: психология и педагогика*, (1 (18)), 20-21.
35. Фомина, М. А., & Бекназарова, М. К. (2021, January). МЕДИЦИНСКИЕ ТЕКСТЫ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. In *The 5th International scientific and practical conference "World science: problems, prospects and innovations" (January 27-29, 2021) Perfect Publishing, Toronto, Canada. 2021. 1300 p.* (p. 1158).
36. Фомина, М. А., & Тураев, А. Ю. (2020). ЛИМЕРИКИ КАК ПОЛЕЗНОЕ РАЗВЛЕЧЕНИЕ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 60-66).
37. Fomina, M. (2023). ADABIY ASARLARDAN KIRIB KELGAN SO 'Z BIRIKMALARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI DEONTOLOGIK MA'NOSI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(10), 284-286.
38. Фомина, М. А. (2023). Роль приставок в медицинской терминологии. *Science and Education*, 4(2), 1696-1699.
39. Fomina, M. A. (2022). The English Language in Medical High School. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION*, 1(4), 170-171.
40. Ahmadjonovna, R. S., Genjibaevna, A. P., Saydullaevna, N. N., Atakulovna, R. N., & Sadulayevna, I. D. (2021). The Teacher's Role in the Effective Organization of the Lesson Process in Foreign Language. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 3072-3078.
41. Shamsiyev, K., Olimzoda, P., Saidova, K., & Ibragimova, D. (2023, February). APPROACHES TO TEACHING ACADEMIC WRITING. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 31-34).
42. Dilbar, I., & Kamola, S. (2022). TEACHING ENGLISH METHODS. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 7(5).
43. Saidova, K., Ibragimova, D., Olimzoda, P., & Shamsiyev, K. (2023). INFLUENCE OF USING GAMES ON ENGLISH LESSONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 54-58.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-2, Issue-1

44. Sadullayevna, I. D. (2022). PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT QOBILİYATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(2), 129-133.
45. Kakhramon, S., Dilbar, I., & Kamola, S. (2023). TERMINOLOGY AS A SPECIAL BRANCH OF LANGUAGE. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(4), 46-49.
46. Ibragimova, D. S., Saidova, K. I., & Olimzoda, P. THE EFFICACY OF PROFICIENT READING STRATEGIES IN ENHANCING READING COMPETENCIES.
47. Saydullaevna, I. D., & Abbas, H. (2023, November). PRESCRIPTION, STRUCTURE OF PRESCRIPTION, USE OF GENDER SINGULAR AND PLURAL IN PRESCRIPTION. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 222-225).

